

The Hunter as the Conservator: Views on the Conservation of Nature in the Select *Shikar* Writings of Kenneth Anderson

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Abstract

Hunting has been regarded as an age-old sport by the people all over the world. India too has a legacy of hunting owing to its erstwhile dense forests. The arrival of the British Raj System brought hunting as an official sport in India. That had led to the rise of several hunters. Many hunters, amateur and professional, combed the dense Indian jungles to practice their hunting skills. A few of them even took to write their *shikar* hunting adventures. One such hunter is Kenneth Anderson. Though he was a hunter, his hunting was limited to killing man eaters and rogue elephants. In contrast to typical hunters, Kenneth Anderson remained an admirer of nature owing to his likings for forest, his views on conservation and his practice of hunting troublesome animals only. Along with his numerous adventures of hunting man eaters and other wild animals in the forests of Southern India, Anderson also gives a valuable message for the need to conserve forests and wild life in his *Shikar* Literature. This article makes an effort to evaluate Kenneth Anderson's message of Nature Conservation in some of his *Shikar* (Hunting) Literature.

Keywords Hunting, Shikar Literature, Man-eaters, Nature protector, Kenneth Anderson.

Introduction

Shikar literature has been one of the less read and easily ignored genres of literature. The reasons for this tendency are obvious: first, hunting has been banned-not only in India but also in the entire world. Second, there is a dearth of knowledge regarding the shikar literature that has come up in different languages and its significance both from aesthetical point of view and from the point of conservation of nature. Third, sometimes shikar literature receives criticism as a record of wanton killing of wild animals. Finally, questions are also posed against the authenticity behind such narratives. We should also remember that any writing that has not been classified as "classical" or which has not been included for academic discussion normally gets passed over as not important at all. However, Shikar literature is a very unique genre of writing. It cannot be written just by an amalgamation of imagination, creativity and mastery over language. An acute awareness about forests, flora and fauna, animal behaviour and their routine, food habits of animals etc are needed along with a thorough experience in hunting. From this perspective, names like Jim Corbett and Kenneth Anderson stand apart in this genre.

Kenneth Anderson stands apart among the shikar writers. His notable works are, *Nine Maneaters and One Rogue* (1954), *Man Eaters and Jungle Killers* (1957), *The Black Panther of Shivanipalli and Other Adventures of the Indian Jungle* (1959), *The Call of the Man Eater* (1961), *This is the Jungle* (1964), *The Tiger Roars* (1967), *Tales from the Indian Jungle* (1970) and *Jungles Long Ago* (1976) published posthumously. Most of the stories of Kenneth Anderson are about killing man-eaters and panthers. However, he also mentions his encounters with rogue elephants, bisons and sloth bears. There are also stories about Indian wild dogs, hyenas and other animals. Being an ardent lover of nature, he even explains the particular behaviour of these wild animals in his books.

Objective of study

1. To identify views of conservation of nature in the select works of Kenneth Anderson.
2. To find out ecocritical perspectives in the shikar narratives of Kenneth Anderson.

3. To distinguish the works of Anderson from other hunters with regard to their views and opinions on hunting.

Review of Literature

In his article, "The Aporia in the Writings of Jim Corbett: The Paradox of Preservation and Destruction" Tuhin Sengupta compares Jim Corbett and Kenneth Anderson. Gupta opines that Jim Corbett, a British hunter regarded for his hunting man-eaters. Like, Kenneth Anderson, Jim Corbett too advocated the conservation of wildlife. Jim Corbett also tells shooting through camera is always better than gun shooting. Tuhin Sengupta tells, "Corbett never puts the blame on the poor animal. He calmly unveils the secrets of its turning into one and begs pardon for it" [1]. In this article Sengupta tries to find out the main differences between the two brave British hunters- Kenneth Anderson and Jim Corbett. Sengupta points out that Anderson has come from urban background where as Jim Corbett from rural. In the conclusion of his article, Tuhin tells that, "Corbett was the best hunter at his time; but his works must be read as something important and literary and not as thrilling adventure tales" [2].

Bidhan Mondal's article titled "The Environmental Law of Jungle: An Eco-critical Reading of Kenneth Anderson's Hunting Narratives" sees the shikar literature of Anderson in the eco-critical perspectives. This article describes Anderson as a keen observer and as a good reader of animals. In Bidhan's opinion Anderson knows all the rules and laws of jungles. The books of Anderson give a good deal of information about the local communities, villages and other geographical areas. The article focuses on the different qualities of Kenneth Anderson as a hunter towards hunting and wildlife conservation. Bidhan tells "one may argue that hunting activity is against the ethics of ecocriticism as killing the animals, means affecting the eco-diversity of the environment. But one should also remember that these big-cats were man-eaters and they had killed more than 1000 villagers, from this perspective shooting man-eaters is a responsible task, undertaken to save villagers" [3]. Bidhan concludes his article writing Anderson is a great hunter who emphasizes conservation of forests, wildlife and nature.

Talking about the rules passed by the Indian Government just a few decades before independence to ban hunting and conserve nature, Kavya Chimalgi opines that after the 1910s, game reserves began to operate according to strict rules; previously where shooting of animals and their young was encouraged with hefty bounties, the practice was now banned. Initially, this practice was just to ensure that a steady amount of game remained but it grew into a conservation movement, which was supported by hunter – turned-conservationists such as Jim Corbett, A.A. Dunbar Brander, Kenneth Anderson and the likes. The only animals they shot were those that were declared man-eaters. (pp6-7).

Main Text

The Hunter as the Conservator: *Tales from the Jungle*

Tales from the Jungle(1970) contains eight short stories by Kenneth Anderson. At first, we have "*Ghooming at Dawn*". It narrates a shikar's walk in the jungle with a fascinating description of the jungle and its denizens. The next story is "*The Bellundur Ogre*", named after the adventure of killing a man-eater who made its presence felt near the Bellundur hamlet in Shimoga district of Karnataka. In this narrative, Anderson claims he only ever went after confirmed man-eaters. I do not know if even that is morally justifiable. "The Aristocrat of Amligola" is the story of transformation of a tiger from a lazy, confident tiger, given to sunning on rocks in plain view to a vicious, scheming, cowardly man-eater, after being partially blinded in a human attack.

"*The Assassin of Diguva Metta*" is set in Andhra, in which Anderson recounts his hunting of a man-eater panther that used to haunt people around the railway line, and kill in the pandemonium caused by incoming trains. In "Tales of the Supernatural", the author takes us through some of his paranormal experiences and gives his valuable insights. "*The Strange Case of the Gerhetti Leopard*" and "*The Lakkavali Man-eater*" take us through the account of hunting a leopard and tiger that became man-eaters after the misadventures of inexperienced hunters. "What the Thunderstorm Brought" recounts a photography expedition with his son, in which an elephant and a tiger attack his hideout on a tree.

These stories present us a varied picture of the knowledge Kenneth Anderson possessed about the wild animals, especially the species he hunted. The details he provides certainly speak volumes about his rich experience in jungle. In "*The Bellundur Ogre*", he writes that "the noise made by a feeding tiger indicates its mood. Generally, it is one of great contentment, and the sounds of mastication, gnawing, chewing and the tearing and rending of flesh follow one another as the feast progresses". In "*The Aristocrat of Amligola*", he writes about the behaviour of tigers during mating season, "tigers can be very dangerous if encountered in the mating season in company with their newly found spouses" " I oppose hunting tigers that have not molested man...the Gowndanorai might

never become a man-eater ...". These details not only give a fascinating reading to the reader but also an invaluable information about animal behaviour.

When it comes to the question of hunting, Anderson does possess his own sense of understanding and principles. For instance, in the story, *"The Assassin of Diguva Metta"* he asserts that he dislikes using dogs as bait as "They are far too sensitive and suffer an agony of apprehension when chained up, as they appear to realize the danger they are in". He also provides us a valuable information regarding the behaviour of panthers: "with a panther the risk was less: the more timid but also more cunning, it waits for the victim who is alone and helpless before launching its attack, avoiding showing itself when more than one person is present". This acute observation regarding panthers gets expressed again in *"The Strange Case of the Gerhetti Leopard"*: "panthers being smaller, shorter and weaker than tiger, are unable to carry away their kills clear of the ground. They have to drag their dead victims along, for which reason they do not go far before starting to eat".

That Kenneth Anderson is plainly honest in his accounts is proved when he reiterates that "it is not well to boast that 'with one shot I killed it', for any person even with a rudimentary experience of wild animals will tell you that a sambar can carry nine bullets in its body and move for miles, a bison fifteen, a wild elephant sometimes twenty-five, and a tiger or panther a great many before it falls dead. And it can tear you to pieces before it dies". This solves the question regarding the authenticity of his accounts. In the story *"The Lakkavali Man-eater"* he argues that "it was against rules to shoot tigers on the roadside with the aid of a spotlight, and unsporting besides".

The last narrative *"What the Thunderstorm Brought"* reveals Kenneth Anderson as an admirer of nature: Anderson's reflection upon his son's invitation to go on a trip to jungle shows us him as a lover of nature "To the jungles? What a strange place to celebrate! But the truth is we both love the jungles. In them we are at home; there we find peace." It is also worthy to note his caution that has been stemmed from his concern about conservation. "some enthusiasts have read my books and gone to places I have named, bent upon trying their luck, and it has become a matter of necessity, from the point of view of Indian conservation, no longer to name them".

Conclusion

It is an amusing thing to find a shikar writer like Kenneth Anderson who is a hunter and an admirer of nature simultaneously. We have to bear in mind the fact that he hunted only those wild animals that had become a menace to mankind. Keeping our moral telescope aside, we find Kenneth Anderson to be a marvellous hunter, an admirer of nature and a very unique and gifted writer. His real-life shikar stories of man-eating tigers and panthers (leopards), rogue elephants tell his experience as a hunter and at the same time, his picturesque descriptions of the rich jungles, his love for wild animals and wildlife celebrate him as a great protector and enthusiast of nature. Anderson's narratives give beautiful insights into the jungles of Southern India and the tribes who are living in these forests. These characteristics provide a respectable and unique identity to Kenneth Anderson, keeping him apart from the rest of hunters who killed for sport or for making money and never bothered to conserve the rich flora and fauna of the Indian sub-continent.

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